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ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE PROBABILITY OF CITIZEN PARTICIPATION IN LOCAL DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES: A BINARY LOGISTIC REGRESSION APPROACH

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Abstract

This study analyzes the factors affecting the probability of citizen participation in local decision-making processes, paying particular attention to the role of socio-demographic characteristics and the level of knowledge about participation rights. Using binary logistic regression, the study provides a probabilistic assessment of the likelihood of citizen engagement and examines the relative impact of each explanatory factor.

Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, administered to a sample of 885 individuals in the municipalities of Elbasan, Mat and Patos. The dependent variable is operationalized dichotomously, as participation or non-participation in decision-making processes during the last 12 months. Independent variables include socio-demographic factors such as gender, age, educational level, employment status, area of residence, and level of knowledge about the right to participate.

The results show that knowledge about decision-making processes is the strongest predictor of civic participation, significantly increasing the likelihood of active engagement. Gender and employment status also result in significant factors, while age and area of residence do not show a statistically significant impact.

In conclusion, the study suggests that civic participation is more closely related to cognitive skills (knowledge) than to socio-demographic characteristics. This underlines the importance of policies that strengthen institutional transparency, improve public communication, and increase citizens' access to information, as essential conditions for more effective involvement in local decision-making.

Keywords: local governance; participation; civic knowledge; probability

Introduction

The main purpose of this paper is to present the importance of citizen participation and the need to analyze this participation using binary logistic regression. Citizen participation in decision-making processes is a key indicator of the functioning of local democracy.

In reality, the level of citizen involvement is often influenced by socio-demographic factors such as gender, education, age, and economic status. However, it remains unclear to what extent these factors actually affect the probability of citizen involvement in decision-making processes at the local level, as well as whether their impact is sustainable in different contexts. In this context, this study aims to address the research question: What are the characteristics that increase or decrease the probability of involvement?

The objective of this study is to assess, through a binary logistic regression model, how socio-demographic factors affect the likelihood of citizens participating in decision-making processes in local government. Unlike descriptive analyses, this study uses logistic regression to model the probability of participation, allowing for a deeper understanding of the determinants.

The main hypotheses of this study are as follows:

H1: There is a statistically significant impact of demographic factors on civic participation.

H2: Citizens with higher education, employment, and knowledge about the right to participate are more likely to participate.

2. Literature review

2.1 Civic participation as a social and cognitive process

For democracy to function, it is important that citizens participate in decision-making processes, especially at the local level, where every choice directly affects their lives. The level of involvement in these processes in various social contexts, despite provisions in the legal framework often remains low. This shows that participation does not depend solely on the existence of legal instruments. In order to exercise rights and responsibilities, it is important to understand the decision-making processes and the cognitive skills of citizens.

Understanding the mechanisms of involvement, such as public consultations or hearings, helps individuals to understand more clearly the ways in which they can influence local policies, reducing the gap between formal opportunities and effective participation. The way participation is structured is essential to understanding the level of citizen involvement. Arnstein's (1969) model conceptualizes participation as a continuum from symbolic forms to real civic control, implying that higher levels of involvement require citizens who are informed and able to understand decision-making processes.

Studies show that effective participation requires civic capacities that go beyond demographic characteristics, including the level of information and the ability to understand decision-making processes (Nabatchi & Leighninger, 2015). In this context, information can be seen as a mediating mechanism that links social structure to individual behavior. This cognitive dimension is further emphasized in approaches that link participation to the ability to understand and evaluate public information, which improves the quality of collective decisions (Landemore, 2013, 2020). Informed citizens are more likely to contribute to decision-making processes and influence the quality of decisions. According to Sen (1999), development is related to the expansion of individuals' ability to act and, in this sense, information about rights and decision-making processes helps citizens to be more actively involved. When people are informed, they are more likely to move from a passive role to a more engaged role in decision-making. However, this relationship is not always straightforward. Even individuals who have information and resources may not participate, especially when trust in institutions is lacking. As Hibbing and Theiss-Morse (2002) argue, citizens often withdraw not because they cannot, but because they believe that their participation has no real impact. This shows that information is important, but is not always sufficient to foster civic engagement.

The literature shows that information acts as an empowerment mechanism, increasing individuals' trust and perception of influence. Information is not simply a resource, but an element that influences the relationship between citizens and decision-making processes, strengthening opportunities for real participation. Lack of knowledge about the functioning of local institutions is associated with lower levels of involvement, as evidenced also in the Albanian context (Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung, 2023).

Information helps not only to understand processes, but also to make citizens more active, bringing the rights they have closer to their participation in public life.

2.2 Determinants of civic participation

Factors such as gender, age, education, employment status, and knowledge of decision-making processes do not operate independently, but as part of a social system that influences the probability of participation. This implies that participation is conditioned by the social context in which individuals operate.

Verba, Schlozman, and Brady (1995) argue that participation is related to the distribution of civic resources and skills. However, these resources do not automatically translate into engagement, indicating the existence of a gap between the capacity for participation and its realization. In this context, socio-demographic factors should be seen as indicators of social position and access to resources. Gender and age differences in participation are related to the way individuals engage in social networks and interact with institutions (Coffé & Bolzendahl, 2010; Quintelier, 2007). Other studies show that participation is often dominated by middle-aged individuals, while young people tend to engage less in traditional forms of participation (Einstein et al., 2017; Quintelier, 2007). Warburton and McLaughlin (2013) emphasize that older people show

higher levels of engagement due to a sense of community responsibility and greater time availability. Childs and Lovenduski (2013) argue that gender participation is mainly related to institutional practices and structures, and should not be understood simply as individual choices. In this sense, institutions and legal procedures can create opportunities or barriers to involvement in public life.

An important dimension in the analysis of participation is the role of social structures. Bourdieu (1986) explains this through the concept of social capital, arguing that individuals who possess more social capital, through networks and connections, have an advantage in accessing opportunities for action. Putnam (2000) emphasizes that high levels of trust and cooperation in the community promote civic engagement, while their lack leads to isolation and non-participation. This suggests that participation is not simply an individual choice, but a process conditioned by the social context. Aalen et al. (2022) find that employment does not necessarily increase engagement, and in some cases even limits participation in community meetings due to time constraints. However, these factors are not sufficient to explain participation, as even individuals with high resources may remain passive. Similarly, resources influence participation through the capacities and social integration they enable. Education increases the ability to understand public information, while employment creates social networks that can foster engagement (Nie et al., 1996; Lorenzini, 2012). Education that develops civic skills and an understanding of democratic processes can significantly influence the level of participation (Campbell, 2019). At the same time, lack of knowledge about the functioning of local institutions is associated with lower levels of involvement, highlighting the importance of the educational dimension in civic engagement.

Other studies show that the area of residence influences participation patterns, where in urban contexts formal mechanisms and access to information can increase the potential for involvement, while in rural areas participation relies more on informal networks and community relations (Schläppi & Kössler, 2026; Kusio et al., 2022).

In this way, civic participation appears to be a more complex process than is often assumed, raising the need to better understand the role of socio-demographic factors in this relationship.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research instrument

For the purposes of this paper, a structured questionnaire was used that includes five sections: demographic data, questions on information and communication, participation in decision-making, participation in decision-making with a focus on social policies, and perception. The main aim of this study is to measure the level of Participatory Democracy in Albania.

To assess the reliability of the questionnaire, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test was used, which measures the suitability of the data for factor analysis by assessing whether the correlations between variables are strong enough to detect common factors. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients should usually be

greater than 0.7 to ensure that the questionnaire is reliable and we can proceed with factor analysis (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

The results of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test indicate that the data are suitable for factor analysis. The KMO value is 0.844, which is considered very good and indicates that the samples are sufficient and there are appropriate correlations between the variables to proceed with factor analysis.

3.2. Variables and their code

To analyze the factors that influence citizens' participation in decision-making processes at the local level (dependent variable Participation), logistic regression was used. This model is appropriate because the dependent variable is dichotomous, Yes = 1, have participated in the last 12 months and No = 0 have not participated.

Regarding the independent variables, they are coded as follows:

Area of residence is given nominally and coded 1 = Urban, 0 = Rural

Gender is given nominally and coded 1 = Male, 0 = Female

Age group is given ordinally 1 = 18-24, 6 = 65+ years

Education is given ordinally 1 = Primary, 5 = Master

Employment is given nominally: 1: student, 2: unemployed, 3: employed and 4: retired

Knowledge of participation, i.e. individuals were asked if they had knowledge about the right to participate and were coded with 1: Yes, they have knowledge, No = 0, they have no knowledge about the right to participate

3.3. Statistical Model

The theoretical model of the study assumes that the probability of participation (Participation) depends on individual and social factors. The main factors we are analyzing include knowledge about decision-making processes (Knowledge), gender (Gender), area of residence (Area of residence), age group (Age group), educational level (Educational level) and employment status (Employment status).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(P) - \ln\left(\frac{P(Y=1)}{1-P(Y=1)}\right) \\ = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Residence}) \\ + \beta_2(\text{Gender}) + \beta_3(\text{Age}) \\ + \beta_4(\text{Education}) \\ + \beta_5(\text{Employment}) \\ + \beta_6(\text{Knowledge}) \end{aligned}$$

where:

- $P(Y=1)$ is the probability that a citizen participates (Yes = 1)
- β_0 is the intercept (constant) of the model

• β_1 – β_6 are the coefficients that measure the strength and direction of the effect of each predictor on the log-odds of participation

4. RESULTS

4.1 Descriptive data

The total number of participants was 885, with 556 (62.8%) reporting that they did not participate (No) and 329 (37.2%) reporting that they participated (Yes) in local decision-making processes. The gender composition was relatively balanced, with 459 (51.8%) females and 426 (48.2%) males. The majority of participants, 55%, were from urban areas, while the remaining 45% were from rural areas.

Regarding knowledge of local decision-making processes, the results show that 66.6% of participants reported having knowledge, indicating that the majority of the population is somewhat knowledgeable about local decision-making issues.

4.2 Model Fit

A binary logistic regression analysis was conducted to examine the impact of knowledge, gender, residence, age group, educational level, and employment on participation. The results show that the model was statistically significant:

Regarding the Omnibus test, to show whether the model fits well, the results show that the predictors are significant and that the model improves the fit of the equation beyond the constant: $\chi^2(8) = 89.662, p < .001$.

Model fit: Nagelkerke $R^2 = .131$; Cox & Snell $R^2 = .096$, so the model accounts for approximately 13% of the variance.

Hosmer and Lemeshow test: $\chi^2 = 13.770, df = 8, p = .088$, indicating that the model has a good fit between the observed and expected probabilities.

Overall, while the model explains a modest portion of the variation in participation, it identifies key actionable factors that can inform policy interventions to increase civic engagement, focusing particularly on information dissemination and civic education.

4.3 Logistic Regression Coefficients and hypothesis

H1 is partially supported, as some of the factors are statistically significant predictors, while others are not. For example:

Gender (Female): $B = 0.527, p < 0.001, \text{Exp}(B) = 1.69$ → females are more likely to participate than males.

Educational level: $B = -0.242, p = 0.001, \text{Exp}(B) = 0.79$ → higher educational level is associated with slightly lower odds of participation, which is unexpected.

Age group and place of residence (urban/rural) are not statistically significant.

Employment status (overall): $\chi^2 = 12.653, p = 0.005$ → this factor is significant, although none of the individual categories (student, unemployed, retired) were significant.

Table 1.

Results of the binary logistic regression on factors influencing civic participation

Predictor	B	SE	Wald	Sig.	Exp(B)	Interpretation	Support for H1/H2
Knowledge (Dija = Yes)	1.117	0.171	42.545	0	3.06	Knowledge triples the odds of participation	H2 supported
Gender (Female)	0.527	0.15	12.297	0	1.69	Females have 69% higher odds than males	H1 supported
Place of residence (Urban)	-0.008	0.157	0.003	0.957	0.99	No significant effect	Not significant
Age group	0.084	0.073	1.34	0.247	1.09	Not significant	Not significant
Educational level	-0.242	0.074	10.667	0.001	0.79	Slight negative effect; higher education slightly lowers odds	Partially supports H2 (unexpected negative)
Employment status (overall)			12.653	0.005		Significant overall effect; individual categories not significant	H2 partially supported
Constant	-0.201	0.396	0.259	0.611	0.818		

Regarding the second hypothesis, individuals with higher levels of education, employment, and knowledge about participation rights are more likely to participate.

Knowledge: $B = 1.117$, $p < 0.001$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 3.06$ → strongly supports H2, suggesting that informed citizens are three times more likely to participate.

Employment status: the overall effect is significant, suggesting that employment context might affect participation.

Educational level: surprisingly, $B = -0.242$, $p = 0.001$, $\text{Exp}(B) = 0.79$ → higher education slightly reduces the chances of participation in this study, suggesting possible context-specific effects.

H2 is partially supported. While knowledge is a significant predictor of participation, higher formal education did not have a positive effect, and employment status has a generally weaker effect. This highlights the pivotal importance of awareness and information over formal education in encouraging civic participation.

5. DISCUSSION

Logistic regression analysis was used to examine the impact of demographic and informational factors on citizen participation in local decision-making. The results showed that the model as a whole was statistically significant.

Regarding Hypothesis 1, which predicted that demographic factors influence civic participation, the findings only partially support it. Specifically, gender and employment status were found to be significant predictors. Women were more likely to be involved in local decision-making compared to men. This may be related to the increasing involvement of women in issues that directly affect the community, especially at the local level, such as family welfare, education, social services, and the environment. Employment status also proved to be significant, suggesting a link between economic integration and civic engagement. Employed individuals tend to have more resources, access to information, and social networks, which may increase the

likelihood of participation. On the other hand, economic insecurity or unemployment may limit participation, due to lack of time, motivation, or even trust in institutions. Meanwhile, age, residence, and educational level did not turn out to be significant predictors of participation. This may suggest that other factors, such as institutional, social or cultural ones, play a greater role than demographic characteristics themselves.

For Hypothesis 2, which assumed that knowledge, higher education, and employment influence civic participation, the results showed that the strongest role belongs to knowledge about local decision-making. Participants who were more informed were significantly more likely to engage in decision-making processes. This finding suggests that information and a concrete understanding of how local institutions function are key elements for civic empowerment. When individuals understand the procedures, actors and mechanisms through which they can influence, they tend to feel more heard and, consequently, more motivated and confident to get involved. Employment also turned out to have a significant impact on civic participation. This may be related to the fact that individuals involved in the labor market have more opportunities for access to information, social interaction, and a higher level of economic stability, factors that are usually associated with social capital and public engagement. In contrast, education was not found to be a significant predictor of participation. One possible explanation is that, although individuals may be highly educated, the lack of concrete information on procedures and real opportunities for involvement at the local level limits its impact on increasing participation.

In summary, the findings show that knowledge about governance constitutes the most important factor in explaining civic participation, while demographic factors show a more moderate and nuanced impact. Gender and employment status are found to be important, while age, residence, and education have a

more limited role. These results highlight the importance of informing and educating citizens as a means to increase their involvement in decision-making.

Overall, the findings suggest that the impact of demographic factors on civic participation is more complex than initially expected. This highlights the need to include institutional and contextual factors in the analysis, in order to better understand the mechanisms that promote or hinder civic engagement at the local level.

6. Conclusions and implications

This study aimed to analyze the factors that influence the probability of citizen participation in local decision-making processes, using a probabilistic approach through logistic regression. The results show that participation is not a phenomenon that is linearly determined by demographic characteristics, but a complex process influenced by the interaction of social, institutional, and cognitive factors. In this regard, only some characteristics, such as gender and employment status, have a significant impact, while others show a more limited role.

One of the main findings of the study is the role of information and cognitive skills in decision-making processes, which turns to be the strongest factor in explaining participation. This suggests that civic involvement does not depend only on socio-demographic factors, but also on the ability of individuals to understand and use them. In this sense, participation is closely linked to cognitive capacities and the way citizens perceive their role in decision-making processes.

The findings also show that traditional factors, such as education, do not necessarily have a direct positive effect and may even exhibit opposite relationships, challenging the classical assumptions of the literature. This highlights the importance of mediating mechanisms, such as information and perceived influence, in explaining civic participation.

Theoretically, the study contributes by supporting an integrated and probabilistic approach to participation, where the interaction between socio-demographic and cognitive factors plays an important role in understanding civic engagement. In practical terms, the findings show that public policies aimed at increasing participation should not only focus on expanding formal mechanisms, but also on improving access to information and civic education. This helps to narrow the gap between opportunities that exist on paper and real citizen participation.

In conclusion, increasing civic participation at the local level requires addressing the cognitive and social barriers that hinder participation. In this regard, information plays a key role, as it helps strengthen participatory democracy and increase citizen engagement.

References:

1. Aalen, L., et al. (2022). Jobs and political participation: Evidence from Ethiopia.

2. Arnstein, S. R. (1969). A ladder of citizen participation. *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, 35(4), 216–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>

3. Bourdieu, P. (1986). The forms of capital. In J. G. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of theory and research for the sociology of education* (pp. 241–258). Greenwood Press.

4. Campbell, D. E. (2019). What social scientists have learned about civic education: A review of the literature. *Peabody Journal of Education*, 94(1), 32–47.

5. Childs, S., & Lovenduski, J. (2013). Political representation. In G. Waylen et al. (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Gender and Politics*. Oxford University Press.

6. Coffé, H., & Bolzendahl, C. (2010). Same game, different rules? Gender differences in political participation. *Sex Roles*, 62(5–6), 318–333. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-009-9729-y>

7. Einstein, K. L., Palmer, M., & Glick, D. M. (2017). Who participates in local government? *Perspectives on Politics*, 17(1), 28–46.

8. Hibbing, J. R., & Theiss-Morse, E. (2002). *Stealth democracy: Americans' beliefs about how government should work*. Cambridge University Press.

9. Konrad-Adenauer-Stiftung. (2023). Youth participation in local decision-making in Albania.

10. Kusio, T., & Fiore, M. (2022). Rural development. *Energies*, 15(2), 454.

11. Landemore, H. (2013). *Democratic reason*. Princeton University Press.

12. Landemore, H. (2020). *Open democracy*. Princeton University Press.

13. Lorenzini, J. (2012). Employment status, social capital and political participation.

14. Nabatchi, T., & Leighninger, M. (2015). *Public participation for 21st century democracy*. Jossey-Bass.

15. Nie, N. H., et al. (1996). Education and democratic citizenship.

16. Putnam, R. D. (2000). *Bowling alone*. Simon & Schuster.

17. Quintelier, E. (2007). Political participation. *Contemporary Politics*, 13(2), 165–180.

18. Sen, A. (1999). *Development as freedom*. Oxford University Press.

19. Schläppi, E., & Kössler, K. (2026). *Citizen participation in local governance*. Springer.

20. Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, 53–55. <https://doi.org/10.5116/ijme.4dfb.8dfd>

21. Verba, S., Scholzman, K. L., & Brady, H. E. (1995). *Voice and equality*. Harvard University Press.

22. Warburton, J., & McLaughlin, D. (2013). Seniors' motivations. *Local Government Studies*, 39(2), 238–255.